

CORRELATIONAL STUDY BETWEEN THE PERFORMANCE IN GENERAL AND PROFESSIONAL COURSES OF THE COLLEGE OF EDUCATION GRADUATES

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Correlational Study Between the Performance in General and Professional Courses of the College of Education Graduates

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Abstract

This study is a direct attempt to generate substantial information that would help all other education institutions in the region to streamline educational policies to improve the academic performance of their students. Moreover, this research aims to know the graduates' performances in their general academic courses in terms of Mathematics of the Modern World, Purposive Communication, and *Komunikasyon sa Wika at Kulturang Pilipino*; to know also the graduates performances in their professional courses in Assessment of Student Learning, Teaching Profession, Child Adolescence, Building and Enhancing New Literacies Across the Curriculum, Facilitating Learner-Centered Teaching, and Foundation of Special and Inclusive Education. The academic performances in academic and professional courses were correlated. The findings revealed that Graduate-respondents' performances General Education subjects were found to be above what were expected which were considered very important because these were all prerequisites before taking the major subjects. This means that performing above expectations in General Education subjects indicates that the graduate respondents have a strong academic foundation in essential areas such as Mathematics, English, and Filipino. This foundation can provide a solid basis for their more specialized studies in their majors. Moreover, the performances of the graduate respondents in Professional Education subjects were also above expectations, which were attributed to their strong foundation in the Basic or General Education subjects. This means that the investment in building a strong foundation through General Education has positively impacted the graduate-respondents' performance in Professional Education, reinforcing the importance of a well-rounded education in preparing students for their future endeavors. Performances of the Graduate-respondents in General Education subjects such as Mathematics of the Modern World and Purposive Communication were significantly linked to their performances in Professional subjects such as Assessment of Student Learning, Child Adolescence, Building and Enhancing, Teaching Profession and Facilitating Learning.

Keywords: *professional education courses, general education courses, correlational study*

Introduction

Student's academic performance have been the area of interest for higher education institutions. Investigation of factors related to the academic performance of university students become a topic of growing interest in higher educational circle (Shahzadi, 2011).CHED Memorandum Order No.30, series 2004 states that "quality pre-service teacher education is a key factor in quality Philippine education". The quality of pre-service training greatly depends upon the teachers who are properly prepared to undertake the various important roles and functions of the teaching profession. Indeed, the higher education system recognizes the two most essential factors of the teacher education enterprise – the teacher and the learner.

Professional education, as explained by Aquino (2003), is the heart of the program. In this area, the student is taught the secrets of the "art of teaching" and is equipped with the knowledge, skills, abilities, and attitudes necessary to understand the learner and the learning process. She is taught to choose what to teach and how to teach, how to make learners learn, how to evaluate their performance, how to do research, how to improve instruction. The student will learn all these in theory and practice. The professional education subjects tested in the LET are: Foundation of Education and Human Growth and Development, Principles and Strategies of Teaching, Measurement, and Evaluation, and Social Philosophies. Aquino (2003) describes general education as an area of teacher education program that aims to make students knowledgeable and well informed, able to think critically, communicate effectively, and live a rich and responsible life in a free society. It will touch on various fields of learning like social sciences, natural sciences, mathematics, arts, music, languages, and philosophy.

The study of Dela Rosa et al. (2021) analyzed the academic performance of education graduates in general education, professional education, and specialization courses. The graduates were with a very good high school scholastic standing. The majority were graduates of public schools with CAT scores between the scales of 50 – 74 PR. Only a few received awards while most were recipients of various scholarships and grants. Majority finished the course enrolled within 4 years and took the LET immediately after graduation, they obtained a good high school academic performance. The respondents obtained a rating of good in the general education, professional education, and specialization courses.

Contrariwise, Specific Averages obtained in General education, Professional education, and Specialization courses, Carlos (1992) as cited by Dela Rosa (2021), independently revealed in their respective study that grade point averages in general and professional subjects had no significant relationship with achievement in teachers' board and public accountant examination, respectively. High or low overall average did not necessarily translate to an equally high or low board rating. This could indicate that grades in college are

not as objective as board ratings. The above findings oppose the results of Oñate (1999) in her study regarding the determinants of graduates in LET. Based on her study, grade point averages in general education, professional education, and specialization courses show a negative yet highly significant correlation with LET performance.

Generally, this study aimed to analyze the academic performance of education graduates in general education and professional education courses. Moreover, as Lipa City Colleges is responsible for spearheading researches and other development. Hence, this study is a direct attempt to generate substantial information that would help all other education institutions in the region to streamline educational policies to improve the academic performance of their students.

Research Questions

This research entitled “Correlation Study Between the Performances in General and Professional Courses of the College of Education Graduates” sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the graduates’ performances in their general academic courses in terms of:
 - 1.1. mathematics of the modern world;
 - 1.2. purposive communication; and
 - 1.3. *komunikasyon sa wika at kulturang pilipino*?
2. What is the graduates performances in their professional courses?
 - 2.1. assessment of student learning;
 - 2.2. teaching profession;
 - 2.3. child adolescence;
 - 2.4. Building and Enhancing New Literacies Across the Curriculum;
 - 2.5. Facilitating Learner-Centered Teaching; and
 - 2.6. Foundation of Special and Inclusive Education?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the graduates' performances in general and professional education subjects?

Literature Review

This part presents the related literature and studies in thematic format to further support the readers’ understandings of the different variables of the study.

The Importance of General Education Courses

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) released CMO No. 20 series 2013 as a guide that defines the New General Education Curriculum (NGEC) in the context of the K to 12 curriculums. General Education is the portion of the curriculum common to all undergraduate students regardless of their major in response to the challenges of the 21st Century. The goal of general education is to produce thoughtful graduates imbued with values reflective of a humanist orientation, conscious of his/her identity as an individual, a Filipino, a member of the global community, and a steward of the environment.

Higher education institutions (HEIs) are allowed to design curricula suited to their own contexts and missions and determine the appropriate means of delivery, support facilities and educational resources to ensure achievement of the set program outcomes. HEIs have the flexibility to determine the appropriate means of delivery to employ in order to ensure achievement of the set program outcomes

Lately the system of modern education has produced reliable scientists and technocrats but has not spawned graduates with the integrity of mature personalities. To overcome this, the concept of General Education (GE) can be applied. GE is the implementation of the concept as a reaction to the tendency of modern society in idolizing the products of technology and tend to ignore human values due to the product of modern secular education system. GE is education aimed in developing the personality of the students in the community and the environment through educational programs that foster and develop all aspects of a student 's personality. Besides that, GE aims to cultivate and create mature understanding in the purpose of life according to the nature of science of all time. With GE, it is expected that students can apply the ethical behaviors and culture when they live in the society. (Nababan, 2014)

After the implementation of GE in several universities in the United States, Cronk (2004) stressed that the concept of GE, in fact, is actually the modern expression of an old idea which is the idea of a well-educated wanting to be a cultured man and to have freedom in accordance with the realities of human existence, both past and present. In general, GE is intended for all people in order to be really educated. The GE opposes academic education, which contains excessive "individualism and specialization," fragmentation of the learning process through excessive "discipline," and the rigid system of education bureaucracy.

Moreover, institutions that are placing a higher priority on general education today compared with five years ago are placing more emphasis on many engaged learning practices than are those whose focus on general education has not increased. When asked about trends in curricular practices at their institutions over the past five years, nearly four in five (78%) administrators report an increasing emphasis on undergraduate research. First year experiences that support the transition to college also rank at the top of the list, with 73% claiming more emphasis on the practice. Service learning in courses (68%) and internships (62%) also are high on the list. (Hart

Research Associates, 2009)

The Importance of Professional Education Courses

Professional Education is an integrated discipline that equips teachers with the theoretical and practical knowledge, skills, attitudes and values that enable them to implement the school curricula. Professional Education Studies is a multi-dimensional discipline that equips teachers with the required practices, principles and guidelines to confidently teach in a school. It is a core subject that a teacher trainee offers to make his/her course complete in order to become a professional (Felix, 2020). The relevance of professional education studies in the teacher education curriculum includes understanding the pupil, being aware of society or one's culture, and having a grasp of the nature of the process of education.

Methodology

This part of the study presents the research design to be used, the participants of the study, the research instrument as a tool in gathering information, data gathering procedures, ethical consideration, and statistical tools appropriate to interpret the gathered data.

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational design to achieve the goal of the study.

Participants

The participants or respondents of this study were the thirty-four (34) graduates of Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) and Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEd) of Lipa City Colleges for school year 2022-2023. The researchers utilized the population or total enumeration sampling which is considered as the most appropriate sampling technique for this study because all the graduates of the Education Department who already finished taking their professional education subjects during the second semester of School Year 2022-2023 were included.

Total enumeration sampling is particularly useful when the population under study is relatively small or finite. In this paper, the researchers are focusing on graduates of the Education Department who completed their professional education subjects in a specific semester, which is likely to be a manageable and defined population. Moreover, it provides the highest level of precision because it includes every member of the population. This means that the results of the study accurately represent the entire population, leaving no room for sampling errors. This sampling eliminates sampling bias, as there is no need to select a subset of individuals from the population. This can enhance the external validity of findings and ensure that they can be generalized to the entire population.

Instruments

Since this study applied data analysis, of which the academic performances of the graduates of BSED and BEd students of Lipa City Colleges for School Year 2022-2023 in general education and professional education courses were used coming from the Registrar's Office, then no other research instruments like survey or interview questionnaires were utilized. In addition, no validation was also taken place.

The total General Education Courses of BSED and BEd Curriculum were thirty-six, while the Professional Education Courses were nine. Three of all the general education courses were selected as these were the foundation courses or the fundamental or core academic disciplines and areas of knowledge that provide the basis for a well-rounded education.

Moreover, the professional educational courses selected were Assessment of Learning, Teaching Profession, Child Adolescence, Building and Enhancing New Literacies across the Curriculum, Facilitating Learner-Centered Teaching, and Foundations of Special and Inclusive Education. The following courses were chosen as these were only the available data that the Registrar's Office gave. Adhering to the Data Privacy Act of 2002, the researchers were only given the Office's approved data.

Procedure

Initially, the researchers read concepts and studies that are important and related to the present study to develop the specific objectives. Various references relevant to managing time, discipline, and routine were reviewed to gather important information related to the study. Actual scenarios and experiences of the researchers helped a lot in the study's conceptualization. For the data-gathering procedure, the researchers prepared a formal letter addressed to the Dean of the College of Education and Liberal Arts (CELA) for approval of the proposed research.

After the approval of the Dean, the researchers also asked for the consent of the participants, informing the purpose, significance, and involvement in the study. The participants' rights, as guided by the research ethics, were strictly discussed and observed. Finally, the researchers also prepared a formal letter to the Head of the Registrar's Office of Lipa City Colleges to provide the graduates' performances in academic and professional education courses, the data needed in the study. After the approval of the request, the data gathered from the Registrar's Office were treated, analyzed, and interpreted using the appropriate statistical tools through the help of a statistician.

Ethical Considerations

Though this study is a data analysis, ethical considerations were observed throughout the course. Before collecting data from the Registrar or any other involvements, the participants received a letter of invitation, which they may accept or decline. The letter contained the study's purpose, the participants' rights, and the researchers' basic information, which they can refer to for any queries and concerns related to the study. The researchers also provided informed consent that the participants acknowledged to assure that their involvement was of their own choice and that no intimidation nor forced participation ensued during the invitation. Moreover, the researchers reiterated that the data obtained from the participants' academic performances in their general and professional education courses and their provided personal information were kept confidential and could only be used for research purposes.

The researchers strictly abide by the research ethics and the provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 in dealing with the collected data. Conclusively, the participant's personal information and data on their academic performances were discarded appropriately after the study.

Results

This part of the study shows the presentation, analysis and interpretation of the actual data gathered. Such presentation is in accordance with the specific questions posited on the objectives of the study.

Table 1. *Graduates Performances in Their General Education Subjects (Mathematics of the Modern World)*

<i>Graduates Performances</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.75 - 1.50 (Very Satisfactory)	7	20.59	3
2.25 - 2.00 (Satisfactory)	16	47.06	1
2.75 - 2.50 (Fair)	10	29.41	2
3.00 (Poor)	1	2.94	4
Total	34	100	
Mean Performance		2.18 (Satisfactory)	

As seen in Table 1, the satisfactory grades of 2.25 - 2.00 made the highest frequency count of 16 or 47.06% at rank 1 while poor grade of 3.00 got the least frequency count of one or 2.94% at rank 4.

Table 2. *Graduates Performances in Their General Education Subjects (Purposive Communication)*

<i>Graduates Performances</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.75 - 1.50 (Very Satisfactory)	14	41.18	2
2.25 - 2.00 (Satisfactory)	19	55.88	1
2.75 - 2.50 (Fair)	1	2.94	3
Total	34	100	
Mean Performance		1.93 (Very Satisfactory)	

As presented in Table 2, 19 out of 34 Graduate-respondents or 55.88% at rank 1 have satisfactory grades of 2.25 - 2.00 whereas the fair grade of 2.75 - 2.50 gained the least frequency count of one or 2.94% at rank 3.

Table 3. *Graduates Performances in Their General Education Subjects (Komunikasyon sa Wika at Kulturang Pilipino)*

<i>Graduates Performances</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.25 - 1.00 (Outstanding)	4	11.76	2
1.75 - 1.50 (Very Satisfactory)	30	88.24	1
Total	34	100	
Mean Performance		1.60 (Very Satisfactory)	

As shown in Table 3, 30 Graduate-respondents or 88.24% at rank 1 have very satisfactory grades of 1.75 - 1.50. Meanwhile, the outstanding grades of 1.25 - 1.00 obtained the least frequency count of four or 11.76% at rank 2. The mean grade of 1.60 affirmed that the Graduate – respondents have very satisfactory performances in their General Education subject such as Komunikasyon sa Wika at Kulturang Pilipino.

Table 4. *Graduates Performances in Their Professional Education Subjects (Assessment of Student Learning)*

<i>Graduates Performances</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.25 - 1.00 (Outstanding)	3	8.82	2
1.75 - 1.50 (Very Satisfactory)	30	88.24	1
2.25 - 2.00 (Satisfactory)	1	2.94	3
Total	34	100	
Mean Performance		1.59 (Very Satisfactory)	

As stated in Table 4, 30 Graduate-respondents or 88.24% at rank 1 have very satisfactory grades of 1.75 - 1.50. On the contrary, the satisfactory grades of 2.25 - 2.00 yielded the least frequency count of one or 2.94% at rank 3.

The mean grade of 1.59 inferred that the Graduate - respondents have very satisfactory performances in their Professional Education subject such as Assessment of Student Learning.

Table 5. *Graduates Performances in Their Professional Education Subjects (Teaching Profession)*

<i>Graduates Performances</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.75 - 1.50 (Very Satisfactory)	13	38.24	2
2.25 - 2.00 (Satisfactory)	18	52.94	1
2.75 - 2.50 (Fair)	3	8.82	3
Total	34	100	
Mean Performance	2.04 (Satisfactory)		

As reflected in Table 5, out of 34 Graduate-respondents, 18 of them or 52.94% at rank 1 have satisfactory grades of 2.25 - 2.00. Meanwhile, three or 8.82% at rank 3 have fair grades of 2.75 - 2.50 . The mean grade of 2.04 implied that the Graduate - respondents have satisfactory performances in their Professional Education subject in terms of Teaching Profession.

Table 6. *Graduates Performances in Their Professional Education Subjects (Child Adolescence)*

<i>Graduates Performances</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.75 - 1.50 (Very Satisfactory)	13	38.24	2
2.25 - 2.00 (Satisfactory)	21	61.76	1
Total	34	100	
Mean Performance	1.90 (Satisfactory)		

As revealed in Table 6, 21 Graduate-respondents or 61.76% at rank 1 have satisfactory grades of 2.25 - 2.00. On the other hand, 13 or 38.24% at rank 2 have very satisfactory grades of 1.75 - 1.50. The mean grade of 1.90 affirmed that the Graduate - respondents have satisfactory performances in their Professional Education subject in terms of Child Adolescence.

Table 7. *Graduates Performances in Their Professional Education Subjects (Building and Enhancing)*

<i>Graduates Performances</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.75 - 1.50 (Very Satisfactory)	9	26.47	2
2.25 - 2.00 (Satisfactory)	25	73.53	1
Total	34	100	
Mean Performance	1.96 (Satisfactory)		

As discussed in Table 7, out of 34 Graduate-respondents, 25 of them or 73.53% at rank 1 have satisfactory grades of 2.25 - 2.00. Furthermore, nine or 26.47% at rank 2 have very satisfactory grades of 1.75 - 1.50. The mean grade of 1.96 inferred that the Graduate - respondents have satisfactory performances in their Professional Education subject in terms of Building and Enhancing.

Table 8. *Graduates Performances in Their Professional Education Subjects (Facilitating Learning)*

<i>Graduates Performances</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.75 - 1.50 (Very Satisfactory)	5	14.71	2
2.25 - 2.00 (Satisfactory)	29	85.29	1
Total	34	100	
Mean Performance	2.07 (Satisfactory)		

As displayed in Table 8, the satisfactory grades of 2.25 - 2.00 made 29 Graduate-respondents or 85.29% at rank 1 whereas the very satisfactory grades of 1.75 - 1.50 obtained the least frequency count of five or 14.71% at rank 2. The mean grade of 2.07 concluded that the Graduate - respondents have satisfactory performances in their Professional Education subject such as Facilitating Learning.

Table 9. *Graduates Performances in Their Professional Education Subjects (Foundation of Special Education)*

<i>Graduates Performances</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Rank</i>
1.75 - 1.50 (Very Satisfactory)	8	23.53	2
2.25 - 2.00 (Satisfactory)	25	73.53	1
2.75 - 2.50 (Fair)	1	2.94	3
Total	34	100	
Mean Performance	2.04 (Satisfactory)		

As given in Table 9, out of 34 Graduate-respondents, 25 of them or 73.53% at rank 1 have satisfactory grades of 2.25 - 2.00. Moreover, one or 2.94% at rank 3 have fair grades of 2.75 - 2.50. The mean grade of 2.04 signified that the graduate respondents had satisfactory performances in their professional education subject in terms of Foundation of Special Education.

As seen in Table 10, when the performances of the graduate respondents in Mathematics of the Modern World were compared to their performances in their Professional Education Subjects, the computed r-values of 0.65 for Assessment of Student Learning, 0.63 for Child Adolescence, and 0.47 for Building and Enhancing have corresponding p-values of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis. In addition, the computed r-values of 0.36 for Teaching Profession, and 0.35 for Facilitating Learning have corresponding p-values of less than 0.05, thus rejecting also the hypothesis. On the contrary, the computed r-value of 0.21 for Foundation of Special Education has a corresponding p-value of more than 0.05, thus failing to reject the hypothesis.

Table 10. Relationship Between the Graduates Performances in General and Professional Education Subjects

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Mathematics of the Modern World Versus:				
Assessment of Student Learning	0.65	0.00003	p<0.01, Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Teaching Profession	0.36	0.03650	p<0.05, Reject Ho	Significant
Child Adolescence	0.63	0.00007	p<0.01, Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Building and enhancing	0.47	0.00504	p<0.01, Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Facilitating Learning	0.35	0.04244	p<0.05, Reject Ho	Significant
Foundation of Special Education	0.21	0.23324	p>0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Purposive Communication Versus:				
Assessment of Student Learning	0.49	0.00406	p<0.01, Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Teaching Profession	0.26	0.13754	p>0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Child Adolescence	0.62	0.00009	p<0.01, Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Building and enhancing	0.57	0.00043	p<0.01, Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Facilitating Learning	0.35	0.04244	p<0.05, Reject Ho	Significant
Foundation of Special Education	0.23	0.19068	p>0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Komunikasyon sa Wika at Kulturang Pilipino Versus:				
Assessment of Student Learning	0.45	0.00758	p<0.01, Reject Ho	Highly Significant
Teaching Profession	0.01	0.95524	p>0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Child Adolescence	0.19	0.28180	p>0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Building and enhancing	0.19	0.28180	p>0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Facilitating Learning	0.31	0.07439	p>0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant
Foundation of Special Education	0.01	0.95524	p>0.05, Failed to Reject Ho	Not Significant

Discussion

The mean grade of 2.18 signified that the Graduate - respondents have satisfactory performances in one of their general education subjects which is Mathematics of the Modern World. The Mathematics in the Modern World (MMW) is a 3-unit subject which is part of the 36 general education units started in 2018 and implemented in all general education curriculum (GEC). MMW involves the nature of explorative mathematics of patterns and as an application of inductive and deductive reasoning. Accordingly, MMW is anticipated to become an instrument for dealing and understanding the complexity of present day living as to personal financial management, making social options, appreciation designs related to geometry, comprehending codes, and fairly allocating limited resources. (Commission on Higher Education Memorandum Order Number 20 series of 2013. General Education Curriculum: Holistic Understandings, Intellectual and Civic Competencies.)

The study of Dela Rosa et.al. (2021) on their study results on the Performance of the BEE Second Year Students in the Mathematics in the Modern World, revealed in that there was no significant relationship between the general weighted average and the level of assessment of BEED second year in Mathematics in the Modern World.

The mean grade of 1.93 implied that the Graduate - respondents have satisfactory performances in Purposive Communication which is considered as General Education subject. In the CHED Memorandum Order (CMO) No. 20, series of 2013 spelled out as the Revised General Education Curriculum (GEC) for 2018, the core course title Purposive Communication generally aims to develop fundamental skills of communication such as listening, speaking, reading, writing, viewing and representing studied and simulated in advanced academic and other multicultural settings.

Purposive Communication in the 21st Century offers an array of activities that will help students achieve this goal. The activities include listening, comprehending, critiquing, and responding to live or recorded discussions, speaking publicly with confidence, explaining authentic passages or text in their own words aided by illustrations in various forms, writing technical reports and academic papers, and preparing a presentation using PowerPoint or any web-based platforms. It also uses different instructional approaches and strategies based on the principles of differentiation, spiral progression, process orientation, information, communication and technology integration, collaboration, contextualization, reflective learning, and visual enhancement. All of these are essential as they adapt to the demands expected from a 21st century learner who is described as multi-skilled in different ways of learning; self-directed, that is, demonstrating leadership skills; a lifelong learner himself/herself; flexible or adaptable to different circumstances including learning styles and needs; creative in problem-solving; critical in thinking, passionate; and possessive of a high emotional quotient. Finally, Purposive Communication in the 21st Century incorporates socio-cognitive transformative model in English as a second language pedagogy to ensure that 21st century multi-literate lifelong learning goal is achieved.

Learning about one's own language can contribute to a sense of identity and belonging, positively influencing motivation and engagement in academic pursuits. Students who can communicate effectively in Filipino are more likely to actively participate in class discussions, contributing to a better learning experience and potentially impacting participation grades. In terms of language and cognitive development, learning and using the Filipino language can contribute to cognitive development, including critical thinking, problem-solving, and linguistic skills, which are essential for academic success.

Comparing all the mean grades of the graduate-respondents in their General Education subjects, it was found out that *Komunikasyon sa Wika at Kulturang Pilipino* was the easiest while Mathematics of the Modern World was the most difficult.

Effective communication in Filipino ensures that students from diverse linguistic backgrounds can fully engage with the curriculum, promoting inclusivity and equal educational opportunities. Courses that integrate Filipino language with other subjects can offer a richer academic experience, fostering a deeper understanding of various topics. Moreover, strong communication skills in Filipino can lead to more coherent and persuasive academic writing and presentations, potentially resulting in higher grades in language-related assignments.

Moreover, some students experience anxiety or fear related to math, which can negatively impact their confidence and performance. Math often requires critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. Students who lack these skills may struggle to analyze problems, devise appropriate strategies, and reach solutions. Math anxiety can lead to blanking out during exams or avoiding math-related tasks altogether. Odogwu et.al. (2015) said that the conceptions, attitudes, and expectations of students regarding Mathematics and Mathematics teaching have been considered to be very significant factors underlying their school experience and achievement. Students' commitment in mathematics refers to students' motivation to learn mathematics, their confidence in their ability to succeed in mathematics and their emotional feelings about mathematics. Students' commitment in mathematics plays a key role in the acquisition of math skills and knowledge. Education Matters (2015). It is agreed by Effandi and Normah (2016), that says students' attitudes towards mathematics are very much related to their attitude towards problem solving in general. They added that negative attitudes need to be overcome, so that later in life, students will not suffer from poor problem-solving skills. It is important to master problem solving skills as these skills are essential for dealing competently with our everyday life.

In addition to this, data from PISA suggests that students are more likely to achieve high achievement scores if they believe in their own capacities and do not feel anxious about the learning process. Thus, there is a clear statistical relation between self-confidence – defined in this connection as a positive self-concept and high self-efficacy – and average achievement scores in reading and mathematics. Moreover, anxiety is clearly negatively related to performance in mathematics.

"Assessment of Student Learning" is a subject or course typically offered within the field of education, especially in teacher preparation programs or educational leadership programs. This course focuses on equipping educators with the knowledge and skills necessary to effectively assess and evaluate student learning outcomes. The goal is to ensure that educators are able to measure student progress, identify areas of improvement, and make informed instructional decisions.

In the Philippines, the teaching profession is typically not offered as a standalone course. Instead, individuals who aspire to become teachers usually pursue a degree in education, which is designed to prepare them for a career in teaching. Education degrees in the Philippines are specifically tailored to equip students with the necessary knowledge, skills, and competencies to become effective educators.

In the realm of professional education, assessing graduates' performances in specialized subjects is essential to ensure their readiness to enter their chosen fields. "Child Adolescence" is a subject that delves into the psychological, emotional, cognitive, and social development of individuals during the critical stages of childhood and adolescence. It equips graduates with insights into understanding the complexities of young minds, enabling them to provide appropriate guidance, support, and interventions. The subject covers topics such as cognitive milestones, emotional regulation, social interactions, identity formation, and educational strategies tailored to the needs of children and adolescents. Active participation in classroom discussions indicates graduates' engagement with the subject matter and their ability to contribute meaningfully to dialogues related to child adolescence.

Moreover, High performance in the "Child Adolescence" subject signifies that graduates have acquired a solid foundation in understanding the complexities of child and adolescent development. This knowledge is integral for professionals who will work with children and adolescents in various capacities, such as teachers, counselors, social workers, and psychologists. Graduates who excel in this subject are better equipped to create nurturing environments, provide effective guidance, and implement strategies that cater to the diverse needs of young individuals.

"Building and Enhancing" subjects encompass a diverse range of skills that are integral to professional success. These subjects go beyond theoretical knowledge, emphasizing the practical application of skills and the development of attributes such as critical thinking, problem-solving, communication, leadership, and adaptability. Graduates who excel in these subjects are better positioned to navigate complex challenges and contribute effectively in their respective fields. Strong performances in "Building and Enhancing" subjects indicate that graduates have cultivated a well-rounded skill set that extends beyond academic knowledge. These skills empower graduates to excel in diverse professional environments, adapt to evolving industry trends, and proactively contribute to the growth of their organizations. Graduates' proficiency in articulating ideas, delivering presentations, and communicating effectively is evaluated through oral presentations, written reports, or multimedia projects.

Facilitating learning is a subject in education that focuses on the skills and strategies that teachers need to create a supportive and engaging learning environment for their students. It is an essential skill for all teachers. By understanding the principles of facilitating learning, teachers can create a classroom where all students can thrive. It can help teachers to become more effective and successful in the classroom. By learning about the principles of facilitating learning, teachers can develop the skills and strategies they need to create

a supportive and engaging learning environment for their students.

Moreover, it can help to prepare teachers for the future of education. The world of education is constantly changing, and teachers need to be able to adapt their teaching methods to meet the needs of their students. By teaching facilitating learning, we can help to prepare teachers for the challenges and opportunities of the future.

The assessment of graduates' performance in their professional education subjects is a crucial aspect of ensuring their competence and preparedness for their future roles. This paper delves into the evaluation of graduates' performances in the subject of "Foundation of Special Education" within the context of professional education. This subject plays a pivotal role in equipping future educators with the knowledge, skills, and perspectives required working effectively with individuals with diverse learning needs.

High performance in the "Foundation of Special Education" subject signifies that graduates have acquired a solid understanding of the principles, practices, and challenges of special education. Graduates who excel in this subject are well-prepared to contribute positively to the educational experiences of students with disabilities, fostering an inclusive and equitable learning environment. Summarizing the performances of the Graduate-respondents in their Professional Education subjects, Assessment of Student Learning was found to be the easiest as evidenced the highest obtained mean while Facilitating Learning was the most difficult.

The high mean score for "Assessment of Student Learning" suggests that participants may feel more confident and comfortable with evaluating and measuring student progress. This could indicate that educators have a good understanding of assessment methods, tools, and techniques. It may also imply that there is a strong emphasis on assessment strategies in the educational environment. The lower mean score for "Facilitating Learning" suggests that participants may perceive this aspect as more challenging. "Facilitating Learning" involves creating effective and engaging learning experiences, managing classroom dynamics, and adapting teaching methods to meet diverse student needs. The lower score could highlight areas where educators may need more support or professional development to enhance their teaching strategies.

These safely generalized that the performances of the Graduate-respondents in Mathematics of the Modern World have high significant relationships to their performances in their Professional Education Subjects in terms of Assessment of Student Learning, Child Adolescence, and Building and Enhancing; significant relationships in terms of Teaching Profession and Facilitating Learning; and no significant relationship in terms of Foundation of Special Education.

Graduates who excel in "Mathematics of the Modern World" demonstrate strong performances in "Assessment of Student Learning," "Child Adolescence," and "Building and Enhancing" professional education subjects. This suggests that proficiency in mathematical concepts from "Mathematics of the Modern World" positively influences their abilities in assessing student learning, understanding child adolescence, and building/enhancing essential professional skills.

Graduates' performances in "Mathematics of the Modern World" also have a significant relationship with their performance in "Teaching Profession" and "Facilitating Learning." This implies that a solid foundation in mathematical principles enhances their abilities in understanding the teaching profession and facilitating effective learning experiences. Interestingly, no significant relationship was found between graduates' performances in "Mathematics of the Modern World" and their performance in "Foundation of Special Education." This suggests that while mathematical aptitude is valuable, it may not strongly correlate with understanding the foundational concepts of special education.

Moreover, Mathematics is a language that can represent and solve problems in various contexts. This makes it a valuable tool for future teachers in all areas of professional education, as they need to understand and analyze data, make predictions, and solve problems. It is a way of thinking that can be used to develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and reasoning skills. These skills are essential for success in all areas of professional education, as teachers need to be able to think critically about their students' needs, solve problems creatively, and make decisions based on evidence.

Mathematics is a creative and innovative subject that can be used to develop new ideas and solutions. This makes it a valuable tool for teachers in Foundation of Special Education, as they need to be able to think creatively about how to meet the needs of their students with disabilities.

When the performances of the Graduate-respondents in Purposive Communication were compared to their performances in their Professional Education Subjects, the computed r-values of 0.49 for Assessment of Student Learning, 0.62 for Child Adolescence, and 0.57 for Building and Enhancing have corresponding p-values of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis. Moreover, the computed r-value of 0.35 for Facilitating Learning has a corresponding p-value of less than 0.05, thus rejecting also the hypothesis. Meanwhile, the computed r-values of 0.26 for Teaching Profession and 0.23 Foundation of Special Education have corresponding p-values of more than 0.05, thus failing to reject the hypothesis.

These safely inferred that the performances of the Graduate-respondents in Purposive Communication have high significant relationships to their performances in their Professional Education Subjects in terms of Assessment of Student Learning, Child Adolescence, and Building and Enhancing; significant relationship in terms of Facilitating Learning; and no significant relationship in terms of Foundation of Special Education. Graduates who excel in "Purposive Communication" tend to perform well in "Assessment of Student Learning," "Child Adolescence," and "Building and Enhancing" professional education subjects. This suggests that effective

communication skills acquired in "Purposive Communication" positively influence their abilities in assessing student learning, understanding child adolescence, and building/enhancing essential professional skills.

While not as strong as the relationships mentioned above, a significant relationship exists between graduates' performances in "Purposive Communication" and their performance in "Facilitating Learning." This implies that strong communication skills may contribute to their effectiveness in facilitating learning experiences for students, though other factors might also play a role in this relationship. Interestingly, no significant relationship was found between graduates' performances in "Purposive Communication" and their performance in "Foundation of Special Education." This suggests that while effective communication skills are important, they may not strongly correlate with understanding the foundational concepts of special education.

Lastly, when the performances of the Graduate-respondents in *Komunikasyon sa Wika at Kulturang Pilipino* were compared to their performances in their Professional Education Subjects, the computed r-value of 0.45 for Assessment of Student Learning has a corresponding p-value of less than 0.01, thus rejecting the hypothesis. However, the computed r-values of 0.01 for both Teaching Profession and Foundation of Special Education, and 0.19 for both Child Adolescence, and Building and Enhancing have corresponding p-values of more than 0.05, thus failing to reject the hypothesis.

These safely concluded that the performances of the Graduate-respondents in *Komunikasyon sa Wika at Kulturang Pilipino* has a high significant relationship to their performances in their Professional Education Subjects in terms of Assessment of Student Learning; and no significant relationships in terms of Teaching Profession, Foundation of Special Education, Child Adolescence, and Building and Enhancing.

Graduates who excel in "*Komunikasyon sa Wika at Kulturang Pilipino*" demonstrate a strong performance in "Assessment of Student Learning" in their professional education subjects. This suggests that effective communication skills developed in the language and culture course positively influence their abilities to assess student learning. Interestingly, no significant relationships were found between graduates' performances in "*Komunikasyon sa Wika at Kulturang Pilipino*" and their performances in "Teaching Profession," "Foundation of Special Education," "Child Adolescence," and "Building and Enhancing." This implies that while communication skills in the context of language and culture are important, they may not strongly correlate with these specific professional education subjects.

Conclusion

The following were the conclusions drawn from the significant findings of the study: (1) Graduate-respondents' performances General Education subjects were found to be above what were expected which were considered very important because these were all prerequisites before taking the major subjects. This means that performing above expectations in General Education subjects indicates that the graduate-respondents have a strong academic foundation in essential areas such as Mathematics, English, and Filipino. This foundation can provide a solid basis for their more specialized studies in their majors. (2) The performances of the Graduate-respondents in Professional Education subjects were also above expectations which were attributed to their strong foundation of the Basic or General Education subjects. This means that the investment in building a strong foundation through General Education has positively impacted the graduate-respondents' performance in Professional Education, reinforcing the importance of a well-rounded education in preparing students for their future endeavors. (3) Performances of the Graduate-respondents in General Education subjects such as Mathematics of the Modern World and Purposive Communication were significantly linked to their performances in Professional subjects such as Assessment of Student Learning, Child Adolescence, Building and Enhancing, Teaching Profession and Facilitating Learning. (4) A program based on the findings of the study was proposed to enhance students learning.

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